
TALAB, TAKLIF VA TAHLIL

ANALYSES FOR THE STUDY OF INTERNET COMMUNICATIONS

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Countless people around the world use Internet services, exchange information, improve their knowledge and solve various problems instantly. Today, regardless of age, social group or stratum, the number of Internet users is still increasing, but the fact that the number of young people is increasing requires large-scale educational and promotional work in this area. In this article, we will analyze the study of Internet communications and try to describe the communicative actions of a person on the network.

Keywords: “electronic communication”, “computer communication”, “Internet communication”, “Combat behavior”

Dunyo bo'ylab son-sanoqsiz odamlar Internet xizmatlaridan foydalanadilar, ma'lumot almashadilar, bilimlarini oshiradilar va turli muammolarni bir zumda hal qiladilar. Bugungi kunda, yoshi, ijtimoiy guruhi yoki qatlamidan qat'i nazar, internetdan foydalanuvchilar soni tobora ko'payib bormoqda, ammo yoshlar sonining ko'payishi ushbu sohada keng ko'lamlı ta'lim va reklama ishlarini talab qiladi. Ushbu maqolada biz Internet aloqalarini o'rganishni tahlil qilamiz va tarmoqdagi odamning kommunikativ harakatini tasvirlashga harakat qilamiz.

Kalit so‘zlar: “elektron aloqa”, “kompyuter aloqasi”, “Internet aloqasi”, “jangovar xatti-harakatlar”

Бесчисленное множество людей по всему миру пользуются интернет-сервисами, обмениваются информацией, совершенствуют свои знания и мгновенно решают различные проблемы. Сегодня, независимо от возраста, социальной группы или страты, число пользователей Интернета продолжает расти, но тот факт, что растет число молодых людей, требует масштабной просветительской и пропагандистской работы в этой области. В этой статье мы проанализируем изучение интернет-коммуникаций и попытаемся описать коммуникативные действия человека в сети.

Ключевые слова: “электронная коммуникация”, “компьютерная коммуникация”, “Интернет-коммуникация”, “Боевое поведение”.

In the analyses aimed at studying Internet communications and describing the communicative actions of a person on the network, there is no uniformity in the choice of explanations even for the basic concepts in this area. [1] A number of authors call it “computer-mediated communication” (L.Y. Shchipitsina, I.N. Rozina, etc.), others “online speech” (O.V. Lutovinova, L.F. Kompanseva). Linguists define it as “electronic communication” or “electronic communication” (T.I. Ryazantseva, E.N. Galichkina). Terminological differences are not clearly defined, many terms related to Internet communication (electronic, online, network communications, Internet communication, etc.) are used as synonyms, interchangeable concepts.

E.A. Zemlyakova notes that the concepts of “electronic communication”, “computer communication” and “Internet communication” are interconnected by hyperhyponymic (uniform) relations. Thus, electronic communication is a communicative

interaction carried out through an electronic channel. This term is the broadest concept and includes the concept of «computer communication» (communicative interaction carried out using a computer, the subject of which includes the concept of «Internet communication», where communication occurs, for example, through social networks). [2]

Therefore, electronic communication includes, in addition to computers, electronic media, mobile phones, presentation tools, etc. The most widespread network connecting individual computers in the world is the Internet, and network communication is not limited by its borders, and all document work is designed to work on computers in networks, etc.

Figure 1. Formation of an Internet connection.

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I think just one example will suffice to illustrate. A typical student would have to go to the library to complete a task, find the books they needed, and spend two or three hours there reading and writing in a notebook. Doing the same thing at home via the Internet would

have many benefits. The student would not have to go to the library, waste time there, but would be able to read the necessary information thoroughly via the Internet and take it as information for themselves (Figure 1). Another example: in the past, if a person wanted to write a letter to a loved one, they would have to take a pen and paper, write the words on it, and take it to the post office. It would take several days for the mail carrier to pick it up and deliver it to the right place. Now, such tasks have become commonplace. With the Internet, a person can do those tasks in five minutes. There are many similar examples. That is why the number of Internet users is increasing day by day, and many nations are making progress in this regard. Experts who surveyed fifty thousand people in forty-six countries concluded that Internet users in the Middle East and China have surpassed the population of developed countries in this regard. According to the results of the surveys, fifty-five percent of the population of Egypt and Saudi Arabia is immersed in the Internet. Not a single European country managed to enter the top ten. Residents of developed countries mainly communicate with their friends on the Internet. In South America, the Middle East and China, users spend more than five hours a week on social networking sites. The remaining four hours are spent sending letters via e-mail. In developed countries, on the contrary, the main attention is paid to communication via e-mail. Malaysians are the most active users of social media, with each user having an average of more than two hundred and thirty “online friends.” The Malaysians are followed by Brazilians. [3]

The external signs of the behavior of young people who are addicted to Internet communications are reflected in their real social behavior. Some typical signs of active users can be identified: changing their appearance with the help of cosmetology, experimenting with their own image, extreme selfies, participating in flash mobs, charity and social programs, voting in polls, forums, volunteering, demonstrating healthy eating, participating in sports events, frequenting famous, expensive

and unusual places, participating in photo shoots, following the new fashion rules, etc. [4]

One of the main advantages of online communication platforms is the ability to connect with people of different backgrounds and geographical locations. This expanded reach allows young people to meet new people, share common interests and establish friendships that would not be possible otherwise. Online platforms also provide opportunities for self-expression and personality exploration, as people can choose their own online persona and connect with others who share similar values and interests.[5]

Empirical research includes two main stages:

- dividing the results of our subjects into 2 groups (active Internet users and inactive Internet users) using a questionnaire survey according to our author's methodology.

- carefully studying the results of our young people who showed high levels of Internet addiction, that is, studying changes in their behavior using the personality traits questionnaire "Behavioral Coping" (R. Lazarus).

The results obtained using the questionnaire "Behavioral Coping" by Lazarus allow us to identify the following specific features of the coping strategies of Internet communication users, where $r < 0.05$ is an indicator of a significant relationship between variables.

Coping strategies	Group 1 (intermediate level)	Group 2 (intermediate level)	R
Dealing with conflict	48	47	$>0,05$
Distancing	49	41	$>0,05$
Self-control	65	55	$>0,05$
Social support seeking	68	45	$<0,01$
Accepting responsibility	39	56	$<0,05$
Avoiding responsibility	48	31	$<0,01$

Planning a solution to the problem	62	69	>0,05
Positive reappraisal	69	41	<0,0

If we analyze the behavior of active participants in online groups, we can see that the most attractive strategy for them is “asking for social support”; rarely, “Coping with conflict” and “distance” are used.

The group of users with average activity often resort to the strategy of “positive reappraisal”, rarely – to “coping with conflict”. They prefer to overcome negative experiences associated with the problem due to an objective approach to the situation and consider this as an incentive for personal growth. They are characterized by a philosophical understanding of the problematic situation, focusing on this situation as a personal self-development.

Participants who rarely use online communication prefer the strategy of “planning to solve problems”, they rarely use “avoidance of responsibility” and “coping with conflict”.

They do not avoid problems, but overcome them by purposefully analyzing the situation and developing possible options for action, choosing the best one from their point of view, planning their actions in a timely manner, taking into account objective conditions and a problem-solving strategy.[6]

Conclusion

External signs of the behavior of young people addicted to Internet communications are reflected in their real social behavior. Some typical signs of active users can be identified: changing their appearance with the help of cosmetology, experimenting with their own image, extreme selfies, participation in flash mobs, charity and social programs, voting in polls, forums, volunteering, demonstrating healthy eating, participating in sports events, frequent visits to famous, expensive and unusual places, participation in photo shoots, following the rules of new fashion, etc..

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